

TECHNOLOGIES FOR EDUCATING FUTURE TEACHERS IN THE SPIRIT OF PATRIOTISM THROUGH THE LOCAL HISTORICAL MATERIALS

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Annotation. The article describes the methods of educating future teachers in the spirit of patriotism with the help of local historical materials based on historical materials.

Keywords: patriotism, history, method, culture, technology, monuments, enlightenment, education.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 28, 2022, adopted according to Decree No. PD-60 “On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” [1], on the 70th goal of the “Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026”, the task “...Ensuring integrity of spiritual education in families, educational organizations and neighborhoods” has been set. In fact, the great task of bringing up a mature generation that will determine the future of our country and people, and its reputation in the world community, cannot be solved without the cooperation of “family-neighborhood-educational institution”. In our Republic, there are unique historical materials and resources that can be highly effective in educating not only the future teacher, but also the older generation, representatives of other nations and religions in a highly spiritual and patriotic spirit, these are our historical monuments, holy places, ancient writings, museums where artifacts are kept. According to A. Madraimov and G. Fuzaylova define the concept of historical source in their work “Source studies” and explain it as material and spiritual monuments from the distant past that reflect the history of nature and society at a certain stage [2.5]. Material monuments include ancient sites, settlements and graves, ruins of cities, castles and fortresses, household items, etc. and as spiritual monuments - inscriptions, manuscript books and historical documents and archival

materials are understood. Generally, the historical source consists of material and spiritual monuments that appeared as a result of human social activity and reflect its characteristics. Historical resources can be divided into the following six main groups depending on their general character and reflection of the past: 1. Material (material) resources, historical monuments. 2. Ethnographic sources 3. Linguistic sources 4. Folklore 5. Written sources 6. Picture-miniatures. [2,8].

When we interpret the concept of “historical material”, we can understand material and cultural monuments and written sources that reflect the historical events related to the activity of human society from the earliest times to the present day. Using historical material in education plays an important role in developing the future teacher’s interest in science and broadening his worldview. In his speech at the opening ceremony of the 43rd session of the Council of Ministers of Foreign Affairs of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev said: “Nothing in great history goes without a trace. It is preserved in the blood and historical memory of peoples and is manifested in their practical work. That is why it is powerful. Preserving, studying and passing down the historical heritage from generation to generation is one of the most important priorities of our state’s policy. This is extremely important in the conditions of the current globalization, in which new threats, including the danger of "mass culture" and the mood of patriotism are emerging, the danger of the loss of morals and values is emerging" [3].

According to the data, there are 8208 material and cultural real estate objects in our country. 4,748 of them are archaeological objects, 2,250 are architectural monuments, 678 are monumental art monuments, and 532 are places of interest [4,3]. According to the State Statistics Committee, as of January 1, 2021, the number of museums in Uzbekistan is 105 [5]. In terms of regions, the largest number of museums is located in Tashkent city (29), and the least in Sirdarya region (1). In addition, there are 19 museums in Bukhara region, 13 in Fergana, 12 in Samarkand, 5 in Tashkent, Navoiy, Jizzakh regions, 4 in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, 2 in Xorezm and Qashqadarya regions. Organizing the visit of our youth to educational

places, holy places, historical monuments, plays an important role in forming feelings of respect for their ancestors, self-awareness, knowledge of their lineage, self-confidence, national pride, respect for their birthplace, and love for their homeland.

We noted above that youth education cannot be solved without the effective cooperation of “family-neighborhood-educational institution” in the research questionnaire, “What do you think has the greatest influence on human spirituality in our society?” 77% of respondents answered “family” to the question. [6,489]. Indeed, it is an axiom that the role of the family is at the first level in the education of children, especially in the education of patriotism. That is why, the main attention has been paid to the family at the state level in recent years, public servants and public organizations have been assigned the tasks of “working with the family”. On the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 1, 2022 No. PD-81 “On measures to work with the family and women, support the neighborhood and religious people”, the main directions of the state policy on the institution of the family and the support of women are defined, including, the task “... strengthening the educational and educational potential of the family, preserving family values in society, improving the spiritual and moral environment in families and increasing their level of well-being” has been given. There is a profoundly meaningful saying: “The homeland begins at the threshold”. From this comes the formation of the feeling of the Motherland from the family. Really, the basis of the concept of patriotism starts from the ground where the blood of the navel of the child was spilled. Therefore, it is necessary to start educating the sense of the Motherland from the family. The role of the family in the formation of a perfect generation is important, because a person first grows and develops as a person in the bosom of the family. Family education, spiritual and moral values will later be polished among people, in neighborhoods, and in educational institutions. It is true to say that the family is a small Motherland that has created comfortable living conditions for people. The great *jadid* and thinker Abdurauf Fitrat wrote in his work “Family”: “The fate of the nation depends on the state of the family in which the representatives of this nation lived.... Where the family relationship is based on strong discipline, the country and the

nation will be so strong and orderly” [7,8]. In order to bring up children mentally and physically perfect in the family, in the spirit of loyalty to their parents, neighborhood and country, parents themselves must first of all be spiritual, they should always read, have a complete idea of our national history, literature, values, art, and architecture. Only then, effective use of folk art and modern educational experiences will be effective.

Taking into account the requirements of the spiritual and social space of the present time, it should be noted that it is important to use non-traditional ways to inculcate the spirit of patriotism in our children. We must use such methods so that the young generation can love the Motherland in their heart. However, we often do not talk about it in the family, we cannot talk about it, in some cases we think that talking about patriotism to our children means educating them in the spirit of patriotism. Actually, it is necessary to understand the essence of patriotism by telling stories about it. But this does not fully express the concept of patriotic education. Educational factors which influence children are now completely different compared to 30 years ago. Because the future teacher of today’s school is not the future teacher of 10 or 5 years ago. In order to instill something new in their mind, we must first be able to surprise them. Islamic culture also has such power. We think that it is important that we can use the cultural and spiritual heritage of our holy religion in the education of children in the current era, when Islamic beliefs occupy a great place in families, because freedom of religion and belief is fully ensured in our country and strengthened in our General Encyclopedia.

According to scientific conclusion that has been proven in pedagogy, showing, demonstrating and narrating the essence of the process increases the mastery level. In particular, the effect of receiving information by listening is 15%, and receiving it by looking at it is 25%. As a result of their simultaneous participation in the educational process, the efficiency of information reception increases to 65%. [8,79]. We have not mentioned these facts in vain. Presidential Decree adopted according to Decree No. PD-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 “Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” [14], according to the

35th aim of the “Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026”: within the framework of the “Travel Uzbekistan” program, the task is to increase the number of domestic tourists from 12 million people and to increase the number of foreign tourists who are visiting the republic to 9 million people. The following fact confirms that lots of attention is paid to tourism in our country, and it is given the status of “driver of the economy”: according to the World Tourism Organization, Uzbekistan ranked 4th among the 20 fastest developing countries in the field of tourism and rose from 32nd to 22nd place in the “World Muslim Tourist Index” rating, was included among the 10 countries with the “most attractive” and “high safety and tolerance level”. The magazine “Time” which is printed in the USA included Uzbekistan in the list of the 50 most magnificent places in the world in 2022, while “The Guardian” (England) publication designated it as “the best vacation destination”. We are sure that organizing the visit of future teachers to our historical cities and holy places, which the people of the world dream of coming to, plays an important role in the young generation’s respect for their ancestors, awareness of their identity, and knowledge of their lineage, formation of self-confidence, national pride, respect for the place of birth, love for the country.

Analysis and life show that the child development is a huge responsibility for parents. We need to raise the role of the father, who is the head of the family, in the education of patriotism, in the education of respect for descendants and ancestors. According to our grandfathers, if the father was sitting at a wedding, event, or ceremony, it was considered disrespectful for the son to enter the house or to go up to the roof of the house where the father was sitting. Until now, most people over 60 follow these customs, but for young people, this tradition is being forgotten. Due to life problems, parents devote very little time to their children. First of all, fathers cannot talk to their children from the heart and sincerely. Studies have shown that fathers spend 8 minutes on raising their children. [9.67].

Therefore, there are serious shortcomings in establishing family education. According to our observations, the following situations also damage family education: the personal interests of parents and children are sharply different from

each other, inability of parents to help their child with homework due to lack of knowledge of modern academic programs and even Latin script, consumerism in the family, lack of traditions that have become a family value, due to the desire of young families to live separately, the lack of influence of grandparents in education. We should conclude from our considerations that the new social situation requires serious changes in family education, therefore:

- taking into account that patriotic, new-thinking individuals start in the family, we determine the directions of family education and ensure that it is directed to a specific goal;

- to increase attention and encouragement to family reading, to publish a collection of books from the series “Reading with the Family”;

- to set the same requirements for the manners, behavior, and dress of future teachers at school and in the family;

- to increase the knowledge of parents themselves about our national values;

- to focus on “family tourism” to break the mold of relations between children and parents;

- to effectively use our religious values in education, to properly evaluate the possibilities of “pilgrimage tourism”;

- to construct the most convenient and effective method-family tree, which means to future teachers who is their descendant;

- we need to be able to put the father in the leadership position in education.

Neighborhood is the second place after family in raising the young generation. In forming the best human qualities in them, customs and ceremonies held in neighborhoods are of great importance, because they embody the value, spiritual world, philosophy, ethics and aesthetics of our people. It is no coincidence that this unique method of the self-management system, unique to our people, has been deeply embedded not only in the language of people since ancient times, but also in their language and in their whole life. We accept the wise saying “Neighborhood is both father and mother” as an expression of this vital truth.

Therefore, in order to introduce new management mechanisms for working with young people, to create a vertical system of working with them, to solve youth problems directly in neighborhoods, and to further increase the effectiveness of spiritual, educational and educational work in educational institutions the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-92 “Fundamental improvement of the system of working with youth in neighborhoods” was adopted on January 19, 2022. According to this decree, the position of youth leader was introduced in each neighborhood and among his tasks, “to educate young people in the spirit of patriotism and to ensure their intellectual maturity and spiritual development” was firmly established. In the implementation of the task, the Decree states as follows: that is “... in order to educate in the spirit of patriotism and increase legal literacy, organizes the competitions “Young frontiersman”, “Young rescuer”, “Happy starts”, “Temurbeks”, “The Queens of Tomaris”, “Falcons”, “Young lawyer”, “Young voter”, “Young deputy” and “I will be a soldier too” actions and trips to military units”. However, meeting the spiritual needs of young people requires the development of new traditions and new programs today. Therefore, we recommend the following directions to educate young people in the neighborhood in the spirit of patriotism: - to open the Telegram channel “I am a child of Uzbekistan” in Uzbek language on social networks and provide short, concise and popular information about the lives and activities of historical figures, great generals, scholars; - to prepare videos that tell about the life and creativity of the heroes of today, that is, people who have reached great levels in the fields of science, culture, art, sports, entrepreneurship in our country, particularly, about their school days, and to organize meetings with them; - to publish books and albums about the winners of the Order “Brave Boy” and the state award “Zulfiya”, who are peers of future teachers, to issue booklets and distribute them in schools; - to implement the project “I study the history of my family”, “I study the history of my neighborhood” in every school; - to organize excursions to historical monuments, cultural and educational places, museums based on a calendar-plan in order to familiarize future teachers with the rich history of our country; - to organize meetings with veterans living in neighborhoods

and villages on the topic of “Let's be a worthy heir for generations”; - to organize ethno-pedagogical expeditions under the guidance of experienced specialists in order to study the rich spiritual heritage and traditions of our ancestors; - to create a methodical manual for parents, coaches, neighborhood experts.

In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 No. PD-5640 “On measures to fundamentally improve the system of spiritual and educational affairs”, notes: “... there is no integrated system for the organization of spiritual and educational processes, insufficient organizational-practical and scientific research work is being carried out to protect our people, especially young people, from spiritual threats, in this direction, the social cooperation of state organizations, civil society institutions, mass media, and the private sector has not been effectively established.” Higher Educational Institutions and all educational institutions should become centers of methodical and practical support for patriotic education carried out in the family, neighborhood and other organizations. In cooperation, various means and methods are used to realize historical memory and patriotic pride. The educational process in the studied secondary educational institutions shows that teachers have developed methods of attracting future teachers to patriotic education, usually for the entire academic year, summarizing in the description showed that: - cultural and patriotism; - sports and patriotism; - military patriotism;

The Center of Islamic Civilization under the Cabinet of Ministers, the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhan Beruniy were designated as the state institutions responsible for centralized storage, research, and continuous monitoring of ancient written sources, according to the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev dated February 10, 2022, “On additional measures to improve the system of preservation and research of ancient written sources” [10]. These institutions keep records of rare resources, digitize them and prevent their loss. In particular, as a result of the scientific expeditions carried out by the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhan Beruniy, it has been found that 43,081 manuscripts in Arabic spelling, 70,323 printed books and 42,870 pieces of historical

documents are kept in 80 organizations. So, there are a lot of historical materials for the future teacher’s patriotic education, attracting young people to spiritual and cultural values, national traditions through such resources, instills love and interest in the history and culture of our country. During the educational process, one should not limit oneself to the Uzbekistan culture and art, one should show its place among world culture.

The most popular direction is sports-patriotic education, because future teachers are worthy of attention for the fact that in the process of physical education and sports, they are focused on training patience, courage, discipline, and the experience of being ready to serve and protect the Motherland. “Sprouts of Hope” and “Youth” sports games ensure the formation of collective responsibility. Military-patriotic education. It is aimed at learning the ideas of serving the Motherland, the ability to defend the country, the history of our great commanders, and military traditions. Various public organizations and non-governmental organizations have also started practical work in fulfilling this task, it is worth noting that “Courage”, “New Generation”, “Soldier”, “Patriot”, “Young Frontier”, “Young Guard”, “Eagles” and other clubs are being organized in all secondary schools by the participation of Armed Forces veterans. During 2022, more than 10,000 events aimed at educating young people in the military-patriotic spirit were held by the “Patriot” organization, which supports the defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and about 900,000 people participated in them. According to the Decree of the President on March 2, 2022, “On the organization of the activities of the military-patriotic movement of children and teenagers, “Support of the Motherland”, approximately 67,000 future teachers participated in the events aimed at familiarizing the members of the “Support of the Motherland” detachment with the activities of the organization in Higher Education Institutions, in cooperation with the department and departments of the “Patriot” organization for defense affairs. [11]. We can include the following forms of patriotic education outside the classroom:

- to publish wall newspapers, write essays dedicated to historical dates and birthdays of our great ancestors;

- to organize the “Support of the Motherland” military sports games;
- to visit military units, exhibitions, museums and theater;
- to open circles of artistic, decorative and practical creativity;
- artistic amateur contests and various competitions;
- to organize meetings with soldiers, veterans, local intellectuals;
- thematic class hours;

Thus, if team competitions are organized, if each team’s name, slogan, badge, and anthem are introduced, the cohesion of the team will increase even more. In conclusion, we should note that patriotism, the unity of the people and the state territory, protecting the Motherland, friendship, labor, inter-ethnic relations, neighborhood, hometown, family, and work are not abstract things for modern future teachers. These concepts have clear, real meaning and are important in further developing their views and beliefs.

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